

Review

Entrepreneurship Education: The Questions of What, When, and How.

Norliana Abd Majid^{1*}, Fakhru Anwar Zainol², and Nuradilah Abdul Wahab³

1 Affiliation ²; fakhruanwar@unisza.edu.my

2 Affiliation ³; adilaphd@yahoo.com

* Correspondence: nurliana.unisza@gmail.com

Received: 22 April 2019; Accepted: 2 June 2019; Published: 30 June 2019

Abstract: The various efforts of the Malaysian government to produce more entrepreneurs among the youth have unfortunately failed to achieve the intended impact. A report by the Malaysian Ministry of Higher Education in 2017, shows that only 2% of university graduates opt to become entrepreneurs. Furthermore, the International Labor Organization reports the Malaysian youth unemployment in 2017, represents a staggering number of 237,400 persons. These statistics raise questions on the role of Malaysian entrepreneurship education in producing new entrepreneurs. Hence, this conceptual paper attempts to explore the role of entrepreneurship education by clarifying the important elements in education and examining the impact on entrepreneurial intention as the best determinant of entrepreneurial behaviour. By reviewing the secondary data from various articles and books, this research illustrates the key findings graphically. The result of this paper indicates that entrepreneurship education should be cultivated at an early age to ensure adequate exposure to entrepreneurial skills and knowledge. This paper also suggests ways and approaches to reveal young individuals with entrepreneurial intention, which is identified as the best predictor of entrepreneurial behaviour. Ultimately, through the findings of this research, the authors aim to deliver the best methods of educating young individuals to encourage them to become entrepreneurs.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship Education; Entrepreneurial Knowledge; Entrepreneurial Skills; Entrepreneurial Intention; Entrepreneurial Behaviour

1. Introduction

Due to the competitive nature of employment industry, entrepreneurship is the best way to evade the expectation of wage employment and simultaneously avoid being unemployed. Hence, entrepreneurship education is crucial in developing a future entrepreneur based on the opinion by most prominent scholars that entrepreneurs can be formed and not be born (Gartner, 1988); (F. Drucker, 1993). Most scholars affirmed that entrepreneurship can be educated and taught, and not influenced by genetic factors (F. Drucker, 1993). In developing entrepreneurs, the importance of entrepreneurship education is undeniable when previous researches show that entrepreneurship education can increase entrepreneurial interest, skills, attitude and culture amongst students. Specifically, most prior researches examine the impact of entrepreneurship education towards entrepreneurial intention which identified as the best determinant of entrepreneurial behavior, suggested by the Theory of Planned Behavior.

The research conducted by Badariah, Abdul Rahim, and Mariana (2016) found that entrepreneurial activities and entrepreneurial skills can be nurtured through entrepreneurship education and training. In addition, the finding by Fayolle and Gailly (2015), shows that entrepreneurship education affects the student's perceived behavioral control towards entrepreneurial behavior after six months. This opinion is supported by Küttim, Kallaste, Venesaar, and Kiis (2014), who have conducted a cross-sectional studies on students from 17 European countries. The result indicates that the involvement of students in entrepreneurship education has a positive impact on student's entrepreneurial intention.

Realizing the importance of entrepreneurship education, the government of Malaysia conducted various entrepreneurship programs via certain ministries and agencies, which aim to educate whether the existing entrepreneurs, new entrepreneurs, or future entrepreneurs. For instance, Graduate Entrepreneur Fund 2 (TUS2) program and *Tunas Usahawan Belia* (TUBE), which implemented by the Ministry of International Trade and Industry (MITI) together with the SME Bank, to instigate entrepreneurial elements among the youth and accomplish a paradigm shift; from being a job seeker to becoming an employer (SMEcorp, 2016). Thus, as reported by Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM), Malaysia has a highly encouraging entrepreneurial ecosystem (Global Entrepreneurship Research Association, 2017). Unfortunately, the rate of Malaysians' entrepreneurial intentions yielded only 4.9% which resulted Malaysia to be in the 63rd rank out of 65 countries, in the GEM study. This situation shows the steps taken by the Malaysian government and the ample facilities for entrepreneurship activities in the country, still not achieve the intended impact.

Furthermore, the early reviews on literature found that, there are numerous studies from various parts of the world on entrepreneurship education in the elementary and high school level. Conversely, existing studies prove that Malaysia has always been focusing on the implementation and implication of entrepreneurship education in higher learning institutions. Hence, the current research attempts to deliver the overview of entrepreneurship education by clarifying the impact of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial intention, which recognized as the best antecedent of entrepreneurial behavior, in the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991). Indeed, this research intends to answer the questions of;

1. What are the important elements in entrepreneurship education?
2. When is the best time to inculcate entrepreneurship education?
3. How to deliver entrepreneurship education?

2. The Concept of Education

Generally, education is a process of cultivating something to a mankind. In explaining this concept, Al-Attas (1980) stated that, the word "process" indicates the system and method to deliver; the word "something" reflects the content to reveal; and the term "mankind" refers to the receiver of the process and content. The discussion about the meaning of education in Islam revolves within the three Arabic terms, namely *tarbiyyah*, *ta'lim* and *ta'dib*.

The word *tarbiyyah* means cultivating, nourishing and causing growth to a mature human being (Al-Attas, 1980). However, this word does not lead to the purpose of education, because the word *tarbiyyah* is not only suitable for humans, but also applies to plants and animals (Nik Rosila, 2013). Furthermore, the word is more focused on the physical and emotional aspects of humans. Meanwhile, *ta'lim* is a term which intends to teach, train, and educate, whereby it consists of the elements which reflects knowledge and schooling. In fact, the purpose of *ta'lim* is to transfer knowledge without any obstacles in an individual. On the other hand, the word *ta'dib* expresses the meaning of improve, educate, discipline, and

punish. This term reflects the concept of education, which explained by the approach to convey the process of educating humans intellectually, spiritually and socially (Al-Attas, 1980).

Although, the three terms are closely related to the meaning of education, but the term *ta'dib* is more precise to reveal the human educational concept (Nik Rosila, 2013). The word *ta'dib* is also used by the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) when he said: *My Lord has taught me and made my education best*. This Hadith suggests that the concept of education in Islam is to cultivate manners in a human being so as to discipline the mind and soul as well as the cultivation of good qualities in both mind and soul (Golmohammadian, Nasab, Nejad, & Moyedfar, 2014). On the same note, education in Islam seeks to harmonize between the good and bad nature of a human being to ensure the balance of human body's development, mind and soul (Qazi Nusrat, 2012). Hence, the word *ta'dib* is clearly describes the concept of education in this research, due to the ultimate goal of education, which stated to know Allah.

The *ta'dib* concept expressed by the three elements in education, namely (1) mankind or receiver; (2) content or knowledge, and (3) process or method to deliver (Al-Attas, 1980). The first element, which refers to a human being as the receiver of education, whereby it explained by the physically and spiritually. This means a mankind consists of body and soul (Nik Rosila, 2013). In this research, a receiver of entrepreneurship education is a student expected to become entrepreneur in the future. Hence, the researchers proposes entrepreneurial intention to measure the recipient in receiving entrepreneurship education.

Meanwhile, the second element reveals the content or knowledge as crucial in education process. Al-Attas (1980), stated that the content of education depends on the purpose of seeking education itself. Due to the purpose of learning entrepreneurship, the current research recommends entrepreneurial knowledge to represent this second element. To complete the education process, the third element of education becomes pivotal. Education requires a suitable method to deliver the content to the target person (Golmohammadian et al., 2014). Hence, the method explains how the knowledge can be effectively transferred into humankind. Therefore, this research adapts involvement as the suitable method in revealing the entrepreneurship education. Ultimately, this research illustrates the three elements of education as suggested by al-Attas presented by the figure 1 below. The method postulates as mediator as the intervention process which explains the relationship between the content and receiver.

Figure 1: The Elements of Education

3. The First Element of Education (Receiver)

In education, the critical issue is the impact on mankind. In other words, the human capital development is the main agenda in education, and students reflect this element. The measurement of a successful education depends on the impact received by the students (Noraishah, 2013). Therefore, this research argues that in entrepreneurship education, the measurement of entrepreneurial intention is essential to examine the effectiveness of the entrepreneurship education received. This is because, the

ultimate goal of entrepreneurship education is to establish future entrepreneurs. Even, this opinion is agreed by the prominent scholars in the Theory of Planned Behaviour (Norliana, Fakhru Anwar, Wan Norhayate, Norfadzilah, & Asyraf, 2018).

Entrepreneurial intention (EI) refers to the willingness of an individual to venture into entrepreneurship. In other words, EI is the tendency towards the decision in opening a new business. If referred to students, EI is the student's determination to choose a career as an entrepreneur or being self-employed in the future (Zaidatol Akmaliah & Hisyamuddin, 2010). Most previous researchers agreed that entrepreneurial intention as the best predictor of entrepreneurial behaviour especially when involves rare and unpredictable behaviors (Krueger et al., 2000; Liñán, Rodríguez-Cohard, & Rueda-Cantucho, 2011; Nihan et al., 2016). Theory of Planned Behaviour is recognised as the effective model to measure the entrepreneurial intention (Alain, Liñán, & Fayolle, 2015); (Israr & Norashidah Hashim, 2015); (Aloulou, 2017). In Malaysia, previous studies also show that Ajzen intention approach (TPB) was widely used in the studies related to entrepreneurial intention by many entrepreneurship researchers by using the words of determination, tendency and desire (Zaidatol Akmaliah & Hisyamuddin, 2010). Eventually, the current research tries to explore entrepreneurship education by explaining the impact on student's entrepreneurial intention, as the receiver.

4. The Second Element of Education (Content/Knowledge)

The second element of education in this discussion is content or knowledge. Knowledge is a systematic understanding of something that is realized consciously and it brings the goodness towards human (Norliana et al., 2018). This word is widely discussed either in the Islamic or western world. From the Islamic perspective, knowledge refers to the word '*ilm*', which derived from the Arabic word. The word '*ilm*' in Quran is categorized in two limits of meaning, namely knowledge which attributed to Allah and knowledge attributed to human. The '*ilm*' is synonym with the word '*ma'rifah*' (perception) and '*hikmah*' (wisdom) in Quran (Amin & Siregar, 2015). In other perspective, Biggam (2001) explained that knowledge is an understanding of something or someone, such as facts, information and description. This term refers to a theoretical or practical understanding of a subject through experiences, education and learning. Meanwhile, Hunt (2003) stated that knowledge is a form of true and sensible belief.

Imam Al-Ghazali classified knowledge into two categories, particularly *Ilmu Fardhu Ain* (individual obligation) and *Fardhu Kifayah* (obligations in society) (Fajari, 2016). Individual obligation refers to the knowledge that must be known and practiced by every Muslims. *Fardhu Ain* knowledge includes the understanding of how to perform prayer, hajj, fasting and zakat. Meanwhile, *Fardhu Kifayah* is the knowledge that must be known and practiced by some Muslims. For instances, the knowledge about corpse management, the knowledge and expertise in certain field, such as medical, law, and business (Nugraha, 2017). From western perspective, some academicians divided knowledge into three kinds, specifically experiential knowledge, skills, and knowledge claims (Bolisani & Bratianu, 2018). The experiential knowledge refers to the knowledge obtained from the reflection towards the environment, through the experiences and perception. Meanwhile, skills is the knowledge gained from the certain task performed repeatedly, and also known as procedural knowledge.

In associating the word knowledge and intention, Al-Ghazali concludes that, intention (*niyyah*) is in the middle between knowledge (*'ilm*) and action (*'amal*) (Mujiburrahman, 2011). Meanwhile, in scientific researches, the influence of knowledge towards intention is proved in many researches and in the various field. Jepsen and Varhegyi (2011) found that the undergraduate student's knowledge about postgraduate program affected the student's intention to pursue their study to master or PHD level in education research. Besides that, product knowledge is found to have the significant effect on purchase intention.

Wang and Hazen (2016), proved that, quality knowledge, cost knowledge and green knowledge influence the consumer's purchase intention.

In developing entrepreneurs, most previous researchers found the significant effect of entrepreneurial knowledge towards entrepreneurial intention. Liñán et al., (2011), found that entrepreneurial knowledge increases the positive perception towards entrepreneurial intention. Meanwhile, M. N. Hakim, Fakhru Anwar, & M. Dahlan (2015) proved that students, who are inculcated with entrepreneurial knowledge will gain entrepreneurial skills and will be more likely to have entrepreneurial intention. Hence, they emphasized on the role of entrepreneurship education to apply the entrepreneurial knowledge among the students in Malaysian Institution of Higher Learning.

Entrepreneurial knowledge allows students to consider more seriously to engage in entrepreneurial career by improving their entrepreneurial intention and persistence (Fayolle & Gailly, 2015). Most importantly, Ibrahim and Mas'ud (2016), found that entrepreneurial knowledge is the most significant factor to determine entrepreneurial intention. This opinion coincides with the research by Roy, Akhtar, and Das (2017), which suggested that entrepreneurial knowledge intensifies entrepreneurial intention by publishing a positive attitude towards entrepreneurial behavior among Science and Technology Students in India. Therefore, the knowledge is a vital element to ensure the mankind receives the useful content of education. Thus, the effective way in entrepreneurship education is to expose the young people with entrepreneurial knowledge.

5. The Third Element of Education (Process/Method)

The third element of education is the referred to process or method in deliver the content. Meanwhile, mediator is a construct which explaining the relationship between an independent variable towards dependent variable. In adapting the elements of education, the method or process will explain how the content and knowledge delivered to the receiver. In this case, the researchers assigns involvement as a mediator in adapting the third element of education; method. Involvement is a variable that have been used widely in various researches, and in many fields. A study conducted by Ko, Kim, Claussen, and Kim (2008) proved that sports involvement has significant and direct effect to influence purchase intention of sports products. Besides that, the travel bloggers involvement shows the significant effect on the intention to purchase the travel products (Huang, Chou, & Lin, 2010). Meanwhile, Lee, Cheng, and Shih (2017), found that product involvement among customers has significant effect towards purchase intention in online shopping to buy medical equipment.

In the field of entrepreneurship, the involvement construct is also indicates the significant and direct impact on entrepreneurial intention. Luca and Cazan (2011) expressed that involvement in entrepreneurship activities influence entrepreneurial skills, resources organization, internal locus control and creativity at once impress entrepreneurial potential among university students who involve in entrepreneurship training module. This significant finding of entrepreneurial learning on entrepreneurial intention is also recommend by (Xu, Ni, & Ye, 2016), who conducted a study on 1018 secondary school students, within the age 12 till 18 in China. They suggested that entrepreneurship education in secondary school should focus on how to enhance entrepreneurial confidence among students. The same suggestion made by Cuervo (2016), who recommended that entrepreneurship education helps to develop student's skills. This opinion is supported by Cieřlik and van Stel (2017), who's mention that entrepreneurial exposure and involvement in family business intensify the potential among students to participate in the business in the future.

In ensuring the development of entrepreneurship in a country, entrepreneurial intentions should also be sowed from an early age as early exposure to entrepreneurial careers (Aladağ, 2017). The effect on students with early exposure in entrepreneurship can be seen in past studies conducted abroad. For

instance, the research conducted by Cárcamo-Solís, Arroyo-López, Alvarez-Castañón, and García-López (2017) in Mexico, demonstrates that children who have been exposed to business projects have been able to remember 90% of the experiences gained. The study indicates that entrepreneurial ability can be cultivated through primary school. While the research conducted by (Barba-Sánchez & Atienza-Sahuquillo, 2016) in Spain found that students at an early age (8-12 years old) mostly want to become entrepreneurs. Therefore, they suggested fostering entrepreneurship at the school age. Also, many other studies point out the importance of cultivating entrepreneurship from the secondary school.

Okoli and Igwegbe (2015), in their research, titled; *Educators’ Rating of Strategies Considered Necessary for Motivation of Potential Entrepreneurs among Secondary School Students*, suggested that entrepreneurship education is necessary to motivate secondary school students towards entrepreneurship. The lack of previous researches on entrepreneurial intention in school levels, and the absence of emphasis to introduce entrepreneurship at an early age in Malaysia, are the cause for minimal participation in entrepreneurship among the young. It is also a sign that entrepreneurial exposure to young people should be initiated earlier. Ultimately, this research proposes the effective way to deliver entrepreneurship education by involving the young people in entrepreneurial activities at early age.

6. Discussion

In answering the above questions of entrepreneurship education, this research provides the discussion and presents the table below;

1. What are the important elements in entrepreneurship education?

The researchers suggest three elements of entrepreneurship education; specifically receiver (measured by entrepreneurial intention), content (measured by entrepreneurial knowledge), and method (measured by involvement).

2. When is the best time to inculcate entrepreneurship education?

The best time to seed entrepreneurial knowledge is during the childhood, whether by exposing in family business or entrepreneurial activities during the school time.

3. How to deliver entrepreneurship education?

To trigger the effectiveness of entrepreneurship education impact, we proposes to involve the young people directly in entrepreneurial activities. In other words, the hands-on activities will robustly give high impact on the intention to choose entrepreneurship as the career choice. This paper emphasizes the way of how to deliver entrepreneurship education by giving the students chance to involve directly, besides learn the theory and facts in classroom. Eventually, the table below concludes the findings:

ELEMENTS OF EDUCATION	ADAPTATION IN ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION
Mankind	Receiver (Students) measured by entrepreneurial intention
Content / Knowledge	Measured by Entrepreneurial knowledge
Method / Process	Involvement to explain the process

Table 1: Adaptation of Education Elements

7. The Proposed Framework

Finally, the researches propose a conceptual framework for the future research. Since this is only a conceptual research, the empirical research is highly recommended to be implemented. Hopefully, the clear findings will clarify the role of entrepreneurship education.

Figure 2: The Adaption of Education Elements

This research advocates the following four (4) hypotheses:

1. (H1) Entrepreneurial knowledge has a positive and significant effect on Entrepreneurial Intention;
2. (H2) Involvement has a positive and significant effect on Entrepreneurial Intention;
3. (H3) Entrepreneurial knowledge has a positive and significant effect on the Involvement;
4. (H4) Involvement mediates the relationship between Entrepreneurial Knowledge and Entrepreneurial Intention;

8. Conclusions

Entrepreneurship education seeks to provide students with the knowledge, skills and motivation to encourage entrepreneurial success in a variety of settings. Nowadays, variations of entrepreneurship education are offered at all levels of schooling from primary or secondary schools through university programs. Educational requirements for entrepreneurs are non-specific; however a strong business background can be helpful in securing financial support. While successful entrepreneurs are well trained in their fields, qualifications can vary. Therefore, entrepreneurship education will deliver the significant knowledge, which significant in developing an eligible entrepreneur. Finally, we conclude that; (1) entrepreneurship education needs to emphasize the cultivation of related knowledge in triggering entrepreneurial intention. (2) The requirement to expose the young people in entrepreneurial activities directly at early age. (3) Entrepreneurial intention is the best way to measure the impact of entrepreneurship education towards students.

7. References

- Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50(2), 179–211. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978\(91\)90020-T](https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978(91)90020-T)
- Al-Attas, S. M. N. (1980). The Concept of Islamic Education. *The Keynote Address Delivered at the First World Conference on Muslim Education*, 16. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13398-014-0173-7.2>
- Aladağ, S. (2017). The Views of Class Teachers on Acquisition of Entrepreneurship Ability. *Journal of Education and Training Studies*, 5(8), 51. <https://doi.org/10.11114/jets.v5i8.2457>
- Alain, F., Liñán, F., & Fayolle, A. (2015). A systematic literature review on Entrepreneurial Intentions: Citation, Thematic Analyses, and Research Agenda. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, (December). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11365-015-0356-5>

- Aloulou, W. J. (2017). 5th International Conference on Innovation and Entrepreneurship. In *5th International Conference on Innovation and Entrepreneurship* (pp. 8–19).
- Amin, S., & Siregar, F. M. (2015). Ilmu Dan Orang Berilmu Dalam Al-Qur'an: Makna Etimologis, Klasifikasi, Dan Tafsirnya. *Empirisma*, 24(1), 131–141.
- Badariah, D., Abdul Rahim, A., & Mariana, U. (2016). The Effectiveness of the Entrepreneurship Education Program in Upgrading Entrepreneurial Skills among Public University Students. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 224(August 2015), 117–123. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2016.05.413>
- Barba-Sánchez, V., & Atienza-Sahuquillo, C. (2016). The development of entrepreneurship at school: the Spanish experience. *Education + Training*, 58(7/8), 783–796. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ET-01-2016-0021>
- Biggam, J. (2001). Defining knowledge: An epistemological foundation for knowledge management. *Proceedings of the Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*, 00(c), 198. <https://doi.org/10.1109/HICSS.2001.927102>
- Bolisani, E., & Bratianu, C. (2018). The elusive definition of knowledge. In *Emergent knowledge strategies* (pp. 1–22). Padova: University of Padova. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-60657-6_1
- Cárcamo-Solís, M. de L., Arroyo-López, M. del P., Alvarez-Castañón, L. del C., & García-López, E. (2017). Developing entrepreneurship in primary schools. The Mexican experience of “My first enterprise: Entrepreneurship by playing.” *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 64, 291–304. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2017.02.013>
- Ciešlik, J., & van Stel, A. (2017). Explaining university students' career path intentions from their current entrepreneurial exposure. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 24(2), 313–332. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JSBED-09-2016-0143>
- Cuervo, G. (2016). The School Counselor Leading (Social) Entrepreneurship within High Schools. *Journal of Educational Issues*, 2(2), 352–366. <https://doi.org/10.5296/jei.v2i2.10296>
- F. Drucker, P. (1993). *Essay based on Peter F. Drucker (1993)*. (H. B. Edition, Ed.), *Innovation and Entrepreneurship* (First). New York: Harper Collins Publisher.
- Fajari, I. A. (2016). Kalsifikasi Ilmu Pengetahuan Menurut Imam Al-Ghazali. *Kontemplasi*, 04(02), 18.
- Fayolle, A., & Gailly, B. (2015). The impact of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial attitudes and intention: Hysteresis and persistence. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 53(1), 75–93. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jsbm.12065>
- Gartner, W. B. (1988). Who is an entrepreneur-gartner.pdf. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 47–68.
- Global Entrepreneurship Research Association. (2017). Global Entrepreneurship Monitor - Global Report 2016/17 (p. 180). <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781107415324.004>
- Golmohammadian, M., Nasab, M. B., Nejad, P. Y., & Moyedfar, H. (2014). The relationship between religious orientation and job involvement in faculty members. *Global Advanced Research Journal of Management and Business Studies*, 3(12), 542–547.
- Huang, C. Y., Chou, C. J., & Lin, P. C. (2010). Involvement theory in constructing bloggers' intention to purchase travel products. *Tourism Management*, 31(4), 513–526. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2009.06.003>

- Hunt, D. P. (2003). The concept of knowledge and how to measure it. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 4(1), 100–113. <https://doi.org/10.1108/14691930310455414>
- Ibrahim, N. A., & Mas'ud, A. (2016). Moderating role of entrepreneurial orientation on the relationship between entrepreneurial skills, environmental factors and entrepreneurial intention: A PLS approach. *Management Science Letters*, 6, 225–236. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.msl.2016.1.005>
- Israr, A., & Norashidah Hashim. (2015). Research on Entrepreneurial Intention: an Academic Literature Review and Classification. *Journal of Commerce, Economics, and Social Sciences*, 9(1), 43–62.
- Jepsen, D. M., & Varhegyi, M. M. (2011). Awareness, knowledge and intentions for postgraduate study. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 33(6), 605–617. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1360080X.2011.621187>
- Ko, Y. J., Kim, K., Claussen, C. L., & Kim, T. H. (2008). The effects of sport involvement, sponsor awareness and corporate image on intention to purchase sponsors' products. *International Journal of Sports Marketing and Sponsorship*, 9(2), 79–94. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSMS-09-02-2008-B004>
- Krueger, N. F., Reilly, M. D., & Carsrud, A. L. (2000). Competing models of entrepreneurial intentions. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 15(5–6), 411–432. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0883-9026\(98\)00033-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0883-9026(98)00033-0)
- Küttim, M., Kallaste, M., Venesaar, U., & Kiis, A. (2014). Entrepreneurship education at university level and students' entrepreneurial intentions. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 110, 658–668. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.12.910>
- Lee, W. I., Cheng, S. Y., & Shih, Y. T. (2017). Effects among product attributes, involvement, word-of-mouth, and purchase intention in online shopping. *Asia Pacific Management Review*, 22(4), 223–229. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apmr.2017.07.007>
- Liñán, F., Rodríguez-Cohard, J. C., & Rueda-Cantuche, J. M. (2011). Factors affecting entrepreneurial intention levels: A role for education. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 7(2), 195–218. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11365-010-0154-z>
- Luca, M. R., & Cazan, A. M. (2011). Involvement in entrepreneurial training and personality. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 30, 1251–1256. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.10.242>
- M. N. Hakimin, Y., Fakhrol Anwar, Z., & M. Dahlan, I. (2015). Entrepreneurship education in Malaysia's public institutions of higher learning-A review of the current practices. *International Education Studies*, 8(1), 17–28. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ies.v8n1p17>
- Mujiburrahman. (2011). FENOMENOLOGI NIAT. *KANZ PHILOSOPHIA*, 1(2), 215–226.
- Nihan, Y., Çak, Ö., & Bige, O. (2016). Ready to Dare ? A Case Study on the Entrepreneurial Intentions of Business and Engineering Students in Turkey, 229, 277–288. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2016.07.138>
- Nik Rosila, N. Y. (2013). An Islamic Perspective on the Role of Education in Responding to Social Issues among Students in Malaysia. *US-China Education Review B*, 3(6), 2161–6248.
- Noraishah. (2013). *Pendidikan Keusahawanan* (First). Bangi Selangor, Malaysia: Penerbit Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia.
- Norliana, A. M., Fakhrol Anwar, Z., Wan Norhayate, W. D., Norfadzilah, R., & Asyraf, A. (2018). Entrepreneurial Intention from the Islamic Perspective : A Holistic Approach Entrepreneurial Intention from the Islamic

- Perspective : A Holistic Approach. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 8(12), 820–833. <https://doi.org/10.6007/IJARBS/v8-i12/5077>
- Nugraha, M. (2017). Konsep Ilmu Fardu Ain Dan Fardu Kifayah Dan Kepentingan Amalannya Dalam Kurikulum Pendidikan Islam. *TAFHIM: IKIM Journal of Islam and the Contemporary World* 10, 10(2017), 103–149.
- Okoli, C. I., & Igwegbe, A. (2015). Educators' Rating of Strategies Considered Necessary for Motivation of Potential Entrepreneurs among Secondary School Students for Poverty Alleviation in Anambra State, 6(14), 6–12.
- Qazi Nusrat, S. (2012). Philosophy of Education an Islamic Perspective. *The Routledge Companion to Education*, 2278(LI–LII). Retrieved from <https://weblearn.ox.ac.uk/access/content/group/cd464c28-e981-4dcc-af89-945b50a3ef48/Digitisation/HD/Philosophy> MSc/Oancea%2C A. 2011.pdf%5Cnhttp://solo.bodleian.ox.ac.uk/OXVU1:oxfaleph019380010
- Roy, R., Akhtar, F., & Das, N. (2017). Entrepreneurial intention among science & technology students in India: extending the theory of planned behavior. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 13(4), 1013–1041. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11365-017-0434-y>
- SMEcorp. (2016). Laporan Tahunan Pks • 2015/16 Statistik Utama. *Banci Ekonomi 2011, Profil Perusahaan Kecil Dan Sederhana (Tahun Rujukan 2010)*, Jabatan Perangkaan Malaysia, 144–187.
- Wang, Y., & Hazen, B. T. (2016). Consumer product knowledge and intention to purchase remanufactured products. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 181, 460–469. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2015.08.031>
- Xu, X., Ni, H., & Ye, Y. (2016). Factors influencing entrepreneurial intentions of Chinese secondary school students: an empirical study. *Asia Pacific Education Review*, 17(4), 625–635. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12564-016-9439-4>
- Zaidatol Akmaliah, L. P., & Hisyamuddin, H. (2010). *Memperkasa Tekad Keusahawanan* (First Edit). Serdang: Penerbit Universiti Putra Malaysia 2010.